

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN CLINICAL PRACTICE

Bukach O.

assistant of the department of internal medicine

Benitska M.,

Kolbun N.,

Zozulia Y.

Bukovyna State Medical University,

Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) is one of the leading directions in the development of digital medicine and the modern healthcare system. Its implementation contributes to increasing the accuracy of diagnostics, personalization of treatment, optimization of clinical decisions and automation of medical documentation. The article analyzes modern directions of application of AI in clinical practice, in particular in diagnostics, pharmacotherapy, surgery, intensive care and telemedicine. Special attention is paid to the advantages, risks, ethical and legal aspects of the use of intelligent systems in medicine. The prospects for the development of personalized and preventive medicine based on AI are highlighted.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, digital medicine, machine learning, deep learning, telemedicine, clinical solutions, personalized medicine.

Introduction

In modern conditions, the rapid development of information technologies is significantly transforming the healthcare system, forming the concept of digital medicine. Digital health encompasses the use of information technologies, telemedicine, big data, and artificial intelligence to improve the quality of medical care and the efficiency of population health management. According to the World Health Organization, digital technologies contribute to improving the accessibility of medical services, optimizing clinical decisions, and improving public health indicators [3].

One of the key directions of modern digital transformation of medicine is the use of artificial intelligence (AI). AI systems are able to analyze large data sets, interpret clinical information, predict risks and support the doctor in the decision-making process. In many branches of medicine, in particular radiology, cardiology, oncology and intensive care, intelligent algorithms have already demonstrated high efficiency and accuracy [8].

The purpose of the study is to analyze current trends in the application of artificial intelligence in medicine and assess its impact on clinical practice, quality and accessibility of medical services.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Artificial intelligence is a set of algorithms and software systems that are capable of analyzing information, drawing conclusions based on data, and performing tasks that traditionally require human thinking. According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, AI systems are characterized by the ability to interpret data, adapt to the environment, and act with a certain level of autonomy to achieve set goals [1].

The main technological approaches to AI are machine learning and deep learning [4].

Machine learning

Machine learning involves creating models that analyze patterns in data and use them for prediction or

classification. These methods are most often used to work with structured data:

- laboratory parameters;
- electronic medical records;
- clinical trial results [16].

Deep Learning

Deep learning is a subfield of machine learning that is based on the use of artificial neural networks.

$$f(x) = \sigma(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b)$$

This approach is particularly effective for analyzing:

- medical images;
- text data;
- audio information;
- large unstructured data sets [22].

In modern medicine, deep learning methods are widely used in [13]:

- radiology;
- ophthalmology;
- dermatology;
- pathological anatomy.

Artificial intelligence is most often used in medicine in the diagnosis of diseases.

One of the most important areas is the use of AI for the analysis of medical images [6]:

- computed tomography;
- magnetic resonance imaging;
- radiography;
- histological preparations.

Deep learning algorithms are capable of automatically recognizing pathological changes with high sensitivity and specificity. AI has been particularly effective in [7]:

- early diagnosis of cancer;
- detection of diabetic retinopathy;
- prediction of cardiovascular risks;
- analysis of lung radiographs.

In clinical practice in the UK, AI systems are already being used to screen for melanoma by analyzing

photographs of skin lesions, which can reduce the workload on dermatologists [24].

In addition, AI is actively used in laboratory diagnostics for [15]:

- interpretation of biochemical parameters;
- analysis of genetic data;
- automated screening for hereditary pathologies.

In modern medical practice, both approaches do not compete with each other, but complement each other depending on clinical tasks [11].

The use of artificial intelligence in medicine is associated with high requirements for accuracy, speed and reliability of the results obtained. Unlike traditional information systems, intelligent algorithms can not only accumulate information, but also analyze it, helping the doctor make informed clinical decisions [2].

AI systems contribute to [5]:

- reducing the risk of diagnostic errors;
- automatic detection of pathological changes;
- reminders about the need for additional examinations;
- optimization of treatment tactics.

One of the most promising areas of AI use is medical diagnostics. Deep learning algorithms are able to analyze the results of computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, and radiography with high accuracy [20].

By automatically recognizing pathological structures, AI systems can [12]:

- detect early changes in tissues;
- create three-dimensional models of organs;
- assess the risk of disease progression.

In addition to visual diagnostics, artificial intelligence is actively used to analyze laboratory and genetic data, which significantly improves the effectiveness of screening programs [9].

Among the most well-known examples of the use of artificial intelligence in clinical practice are automated detection of diabetic retinopathy, analysis of electrocardiograms for early diagnosis of arrhythmias, as well as systems for predicting the risk of cardiovascular complications. In the field of oncology, artificial intelligence algorithms are actively used to analyze mammographic images, histological preparations and computed tomography results, which allows detecting malignant processes at early stages.

Studies show that in some cases the accuracy of such systems can be comparable to or even exceed the effectiveness of traditional medical image evaluation by a physician [17].

In cardiology, artificial intelligence is used to analyze electrocardiographic data, echocardiography, and predict the development of heart failure. Machine learning algorithms allow assessing the risk of myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, and other pathologies even before the appearance of pronounced clinical symptoms. This creates the prerequisites for the development of preventive medicine and earlier initiation of treatment [14].

In neurology, artificial intelligence systems are used for the early detection of neurodegenerative diseases, including Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease. By analyzing magnetic resonance imaging results and

clinical data, intelligent algorithms are able to detect minimal structural changes in the brain that are difficult to detect during a standard examination. In addition, AI is used to predict the risk of stroke and assess the functional status of patients after neurological disorders [25].

In the field of laboratory medicine, artificial intelligence allows you to automate the interpretation of test results and significantly accelerate information processing. Machine learning systems can analyze large arrays of laboratory indicators, identify hidden patterns and help doctors detect pathological changes. The combination of artificial intelligence with molecular genetic research methods is especially promising, which opens up new opportunities for personalized medicine [21].

An important direction of development of modern medicine is the use of artificial intelligence in pharmacology and development of new drugs. Analysis of large clinical and molecular databases allows to accelerate the process of searching for promising therapeutic molecules, to assess the effectiveness of drugs and to predict possible adverse reactions. The use of AI significantly reduces the time required to create new drugs, and also reduces the cost of conducting research [10].

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the role of artificial intelligence in medicine became particularly noticeable. Intelligent systems were used to analyze the spread of infection, predict the epidemic situation, assess the severity of the disease, and analyze computed tomography of the lungs. In addition, AI helped create models for predicting the load on medical institutions and optimizing the allocation of health care resources [18].

Along with the development of technologies, the need for regulatory and ethical regulation of the use of artificial intelligence is also growing. One of the most important aspects remains the transparency of the work of algorithms and the ability to explain the results obtained. The concept of explainable AI involves the creation of models whose logic can be understood by medical professionals. This is important for trust in AI systems and their safe implementation in clinical practice [23].

It is also important to consider the problem of algorithmic bias. If the system is trained on incomplete or unrepresentative data, this can lead to errors and inequalities in the provision of medical care. That is why one of the key tasks of modern medicine is to ensure the quality of training data and conduct multicenter clinical trials to assess the effectiveness and safety of artificial intelligence systems [19].

In the future, further integration of artificial intelligence into all levels of healthcare is expected, from primary care to highly specialized centers. Intelligent electronic medical records, automated clinical decision support systems, and remote patient monitoring technologies will play a significant role. The use of wearable devices and mobile medical platforms will allow for continuous monitoring of physiological parameters and timely detection of pathological changes.

Thus, artificial intelligence is gradually becoming an integral part of modern medicine. Its use opens up

wide opportunities for improving diagnostics, treatment and prevention of diseases, increasing the availability of medical care and optimizing the work of medical institutions. At the same time, the effective implementation of such technologies requires compliance with ethical norms, legal regulation and maintaining the leading role of the doctor in the process of clinical decision-making.

References

1. World Health Organization. Global strategy on digital health 2020–2025. Geneva: WHO; 2021.
2. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Recommendation of the Council on Artificial Intelligence. Paris: OECD; 2019.
3. European Commission. Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare: Applications and Policy Implications. Brussels; 2020.
4. Topol E. Deep Medicine: How Artificial Intelligence Can Make Healthcare Human Again. New York: Basic Books; 2019.
5. Esteva A, Robicquet A, Ramsundar B, et al. A guide to deep learning in healthcare. *Nat Med.* 2019;25(1):24–29.
6. Rajpurkar P, Chen E, Banerjee O, Topol E. AI in health and medicine. *Nat Med.* 2022;28(1):31–38.
7. Jiang F, Jiang Y, Zhi H, et al. Artificial intelligence in healthcare: past, present and future. *Stroke Vasc Neurol.* 2017;2(4):230–243.
8. Yu KH, Beam AL, Kohane IS. Artificial intelligence in healthcare. *Nat Biomed Eng.* 2018;2(10):719–731.
9. Kelly CJ, Karthikesalingam A, Suleyman M, et al. Key challenges for delivering clinical impact with artificial intelligence. *BMC Med.* 2019;17(1):195.
10. Topol EJ. High-performance medicine: the convergence of human and artificial intelligence. *Nat Med.* 2019;25(1):44–56.
11. Ting DSW, Pasquale LR, Peng L, et al. Artificial intelligence and deep learning in ophthalmology. *Br J Ophthalmol.* 2019;103(2):167–175.
12. McKinney SM, Sieniek M, Godbole V, et al. International evaluation of an AI system for breast cancer screening. *Nature.* 2020;577:89–94.
13. Ardila D, Kiraly AP, Bharadwaj S, et al. End-to-end lung cancer screening with three-dimensional deep learning. *Nat Med.* 2019;25(6):954–961.
14. Erickson BJ, Korfiatis P, Akkus Z, Kline TL. Machine learning for medical imaging. *Radiographics.* 2017;37(2):505–515.
15. Shamout FE, Shen Y, Wu N, et al. An artificial intelligence system for predicting the deterioration of COVID-19 patients in the emergency department. *Nat Med.* 2021;27(2):272–278.
16. Davenport T, Kalakota R. The potential for artificial intelligence in healthcare. *Future Healthc J.* 2019;6(2):94–98.
17. Briganti G, Le Moine O. Artificial intelligence in medicine: today and tomorrow. *Front Med.* 2020;7:27.
18. Hamet P, Tremblay J. Artificial intelligence in medicine. *Metabolism.* 2017;69:S36–S40.
19. Char DS, Shah NH, Magnus D. Implementing machine learning in health care — addressing ethical challenges. *N Engl J Med.* 2018;378:981–983.
20. Holzinger A, Biemann C, Pattichis CS, Kell DB. What do we need to build explainable AI systems for the medical domain? *arXiv.* 2017.
21. London AJ. Artificial intelligence and black-box medical decisions: accuracy versus explainability. *Hastings Cent Rep.* 2019;49(1):15–21.
22. Secinaro S, Calandra D, Secinaro A, et al. The role of artificial intelligence in healthcare: a structured literature review. *BMC Med Inform Decis Mak.* 2021;21:125.
23. Ahmed Z, Mohamed K, Zeeshan S, Dong X. Artificial intelligence with multi-functional machine learning platform development for better healthcare and precision medicine. *Database.* 2020;2020:baaa010.
24. Bohr A, Memarzadeh K. Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare. Academic Press; 2020.
25. Panch T, Mattie H, Atun R. Artificial intelligence and algorithmic bias: implications for health systems. *J Glob Health.* 2019;9(2):010318.